



Mean eplSar value of the three taken measurements per sample calculated as a SSFA parameter. The plot shows the difference from 0 to 2000 cutting strokes on the hard contact materials.



Mean eplSar value of the three taken measurements per sample calculated as a SSFA parameter. The plot shows the difference from 0 to 2000 cutting strokes on the soft contact materials.



Mean Vmc value of the three taken measurements per sample calculated according to the ISO 25178-2. The plot shows the difference from 0 to 2000 cutting strokes on the hard contact materials.



Mean Vmc value of the three taken measurements per sample calculated according to the ISO 25178-2. The plot shows the difference from 0 to 2000 cutting strokes on the soft contact materials.



Mean Asfc value of the three taken measurements per sample calculated as a SSFA parameter. The plot shows the difference from 0 to 2000 cutting strokes on the hard contact materials.



Mean Asfc value of the three taken measurements per sample calculated as a SSFA parameter. The plot shows the difference from 0 to 2000 cutting strokes on the soft contact materials.



Mean HAsfc9 value of the three taken measurements per sample calculated as a SSFA parameter. The plot shows the difference from 0 to 2000 cutting strokes on the hard contact materials.



Mean HAsfc9 value of the three taken measurements per sample calculated as a SSFA parameter. The plot shows the difference from 0 to 2000 cutting strokes on the soft contact materials.